

Postbuckling of pre-pressure-loaded composite laminated cylindrical panels resting on elastic foundations subjected to axial compression in thermal environments

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ABSTRACT

A postbuckling analysis is presented for shear-deformable laminated cylindrical panels resting on elastic foundations subjected to combined uniform lateral pressure and compressive edge loads in thermal environments. Material properties are assumed to be temperature-dependent. The formulations are based on a higher-order shear deformation theory and von Kármán strain displacement relationships. The panel-foundation interaction and thermal effects are also included. The lateral pressure is first converted into an initial deflection, and the initial geometric imperfection of the panel is also taken into account. A singular perturbation technique along with a two-step perturbation approach is employed to determine the postbuckling equilibrium paths. The effects of temperature variation, foundation stiffness and initial lateral pressure on the postbuckling behavior of cross-ply laminated cylindrical panels are discussed in detail.

Keywords: Cylindrical panels; Postbuckling; Initial stresses; Temperature-dependent properties; Elastic foundation

1 INTRODUCTION

Shell panels made of composite materials are increasingly used in aeronautical and aerospace construction where strong, stiff and light components are required. These shell panels are often subjected to combined loadings of lateral pressure and axial compression. Hence, the buckling and postbuckling strengths of composite shell panels have to be well understood.

Many postbuckling studies of composite laminated cylindrical panels subjected to axial compression are available in the literature, for example, Chia [1,2] developed a first-order shear deformation theory to study nonlinear vibration of unsymmetric angle-ply laminated cylindrical panels with mixed boundary conditions, and postbuckling was treated as a limiting case. Laschet and Jeusette [3] studied the postbuckling of a deeply cylindrical composite panel under in-plane compression by using finite element method (FEM). Kweon and his co-authors

[4-6] presented numerical and experimental studies for the postbuckling of axially-loaded cylindrical panels with curved edges clamped and straight edges simply-supported. In [4-6] the finite element formulations based on the first-order shear deformation theory were performed and all these studies addressed symmetrical laminates. Librescu and his co-authors [7,8] studied the postbuckling response of thin and shear-deformable flat and imperfect curved panels under uniform compressive edge loading combined with lateral pressure. In the above studies [1-8], however, the material properties of laminates are assumed to be independent of temperature.

For the case of the panel subjected to combined loadings of lateral pressure and axial compression, two different kinds of problems should be considered. When the edge compression is relatively small and the lateral pressure exceeds high levels, the large deflection pattern appears and a nonlinear bending problem should be solved. In contrast, when the lateral pressure is relatively small, the postbuckling caused by an increase in edge compression should be considered. The latter problem will be discussed in the present paper for the case when the panel edges are simply supported and movable.

In the present work, we focus our attention on the postbuckling of shear-deformable laminated cylindrical panels resting on elastic foundations subjected to axial compression combined with lateral pressure in thermal environments. The formulations are based on a higher-order shear deformation theory and von Kármán strain displacement relationships. The shell panel-foundation interaction and thermal effects are also included and the material properties of laminates are assumed to be temperature-dependent. The lateral pressure is first converted into an initial deflection. A singular perturbation technique along with a two-step perturbation approach is employed to determine the postbuckling equilibrium paths. The nonlinear prebuckling deformations and initial geometric imperfections of the panel are also both taken into account.

2 GOVERNING EQUATIONS

Consider a cylindrical panel made of composite material resting on an elastic foundation. The panel is referenced to a coordinate system (X, Y, Z) in which X and Y are in the axial and circumferential directions of the panel and Z is in the direction of the inward normal to the middle surface, and the corresponding displacements are designated by \bar{U} , \bar{V} , and \bar{W} . $\bar{\Psi}_x$ and $\bar{\Psi}_y$ are defined as the rotations of the normals to the middle surface with respect to the Y - and X - axes, respectively. The origin of the coordinate system is located at the corner of the panel in the middle plane. As shown in Fig. 1, R is the radius of curvature, h the panel thickness, a the length in the X direction, and b the length in the Y direction, respectively. The panel is subjected to combined loadings of axial compression and lateral pressure. As is customary [1], the foundation is assumed to be a compliant foundation, which means that no part of the panel lifts off the foundation in the large deflection region. The load-displacement relationship of the foundation is assumed to be $p_0 = \bar{K}_1 \bar{W} - \bar{K}_2 \nabla^2 \bar{W}$, where p_0 is the force per unit area, \bar{K}_1 is the Winkler foundation stiffness and \bar{K}_2 is the shearing layer stiffness of the foundation, and ∇^2 is the Laplace operator in X and Y .

Based on the Sanders shell theory, Reddy and Liu [9] developed a simple higher-order shear deformation shell theory. Unlike the first-order shear deformation theory, no shear

correction factors are required in this higher order theory, though there are the same number of independent unknowns (\bar{U} , \bar{V} , \bar{W} , $\bar{\Psi}_x$ and $\bar{\Psi}_y$) in both the theories. Based on Reddy's higher order shear deformation theory with a von Kármán-type of kinematic nonlinearity and including panel-foundation interaction and thermal effects, the governing differential equations for a shear deformable laminated cylindrical panel can be derived in terms of a transverse displacement \bar{W} , along with the initial geometric imperfection \bar{W}^* , two rotations $\bar{\Psi}_x$ and $\bar{\Psi}_y$, and a stress function \bar{F} as defined by $\bar{N}_x = \bar{F}_{,YY}$, $\bar{N}_y = \bar{F}_{,XX}$ and $\bar{N}_{xy} = -\bar{F}_{,XY}$, where a comma denotes partial differentiation with respect to the corresponding coordinates. These equations can be expressed by

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{L}_{11}(\bar{W}) - \tilde{L}_{12}(\bar{\Psi}_x) - \tilde{L}_{13}(\bar{\Psi}_y) + \tilde{L}_{14}(\bar{F}) - \tilde{L}_{15}(\bar{N}^T) - \tilde{L}_{16}(\bar{M}^T) - \frac{1}{R}\bar{F}_{,XX} \\ + \bar{K}_1\bar{W} - \bar{K}_2\nabla^2\bar{W} = \tilde{L}(\bar{W} + \bar{W}^*, \bar{F}) + q \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\tilde{L}_{21}(\bar{F}) + \tilde{L}_{22}(\bar{\Psi}_x) + \tilde{L}_{23}(\bar{\Psi}_y) - \tilde{L}_{24}(\bar{W}) - \tilde{L}_{25}(\bar{N}^T) + \frac{1}{R}\bar{W}_{,XX} = -\frac{1}{2}\tilde{L}(\bar{W} + 2\bar{W}^*, \bar{W}) \quad (2)$$

$$\tilde{L}_{31}(\bar{W}) + \tilde{L}_{32}(\bar{\Psi}_x) - \tilde{L}_{33}(\bar{\Psi}_y) + \tilde{L}_{34}(\bar{F}) - \tilde{L}_{35}(\bar{N}^T) - \tilde{L}_{36}(\bar{S}^T) = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\tilde{L}_{41}(\bar{W}) - \tilde{L}_{42}(\bar{\Psi}_x) + \tilde{L}_{43}(\bar{\Psi}_y) + \tilde{L}_{44}(\bar{F}) - \tilde{L}_{45}(\bar{N}^T) - \tilde{L}_{46}(\bar{S}^T) = 0 \quad (4)$$

in which the linear operators $\tilde{L}_{ij}(\cdot)$ and nonlinear operator $\tilde{L}(\cdot)$ are defined as in Shen [10]. Note that the geometric nonlinearity in the von Kármán sense is given in terms of $\tilde{L}(\cdot)$ in Eqs. (1) and (2). It is well known that the large deflection and the postbuckling of a panel are two different nonlinear problems. In the former case the compressive edge load is prescribed but the lateral pressure is an unknown and we seek for the bending load-deflection curves, whereas in the latter case the lateral pressure is prescribed but the compressive edge load is an unknown and we solve for the postbuckling load-deflection curves.

Figure 1: Geometry and coordinate system of cylindrical panel on a Pasternak elastic foundation.

In the above equations, \bar{N}^T , \bar{M}^T , \bar{S}^T and \bar{P}^T are the forces, moments and higher order moments caused by the elevated temperature, and are defined by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{N}_x^T & \bar{M}_x^T & \bar{P}_x^T \\ \bar{N}_y^T & \bar{M}_y^T & \bar{P}_y^T \\ \bar{N}_{xy}^T & \bar{M}_{xy}^T & \bar{P}_{xy}^T \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (1, Z, Z^3) \begin{bmatrix} A_x \\ A_y \\ A_{xy} \end{bmatrix}_k \Delta T dZ \quad (5a)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{S}_x^T \\ \bar{S}_y^T \\ \bar{S}_{xy}^T \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{M}_x^T \\ \bar{M}_y^T \\ \bar{M}_{xy}^T \end{bmatrix} - \frac{4}{3h^2} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{P}_x^T \\ \bar{P}_y^T \\ \bar{P}_{xy}^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (5b)$$

where ΔT is temperature rise from some reference temperature at which there are no thermal strains, and

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_x \\ A_y \\ A_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} c^2 & s^2 \\ s^2 & c^2 \\ 2cs & -2cs \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{11} \\ \alpha_{22} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where α_{11} and α_{22} are the thermal expansion coefficients in the longitudinal and transverse directions, and \bar{Q}_{ij} are the transformed elastic constants, details of which may be found in [9].

As shown by Leissa [11], and Qatu and Leissa [12], the bifurcation buckling does not exist when the plate subjected to in-plane compression for simply supported unsymmetric cross-ply laminated plates. This is because the prebuckling deformation of such plate is nonlinear due to the stretching-bending coupling effect. Zhang and Matthews [13,14] investigated the postbuckling behavior of laminated cylindrical panels and concluded that due to the stretching-bending coupling effect there are no bifurcation buckling loads for simply supported unsymmetric cross-ply laminated cylindrical panels under axial compression. However, Stein [15,16] showed that the bifurcation buckling does exist for shell-type structures even though the prebuckling deformation of the structures is nonlinear. Unlike flat plates, the prebuckling deformation of cylindrical panels could be nonlinear due to the curvature effect. Shen [10] reported that the postbuckling equilibrium path of simply supported unsymmetric cross-ply laminated cylindrical panels subjected to axial compression is still bifurcation type when the unloaded edges of the panel are movable, whereas the postbuckling equilibrium path is limit-point type when the unloaded edges are immovable. In the present study, all four edges of the panel are assumed to be simply supported and movable, in such a case buckling load does exist when lateral pressure and/or temperature rise is vanished. The boundary conditions for the cases in this study are

$X=0, a$:

$$\bar{W} = \bar{V} = \bar{\Psi}_y = 0, \bar{M}_x = \bar{P}_x = 0 \quad (7a)$$

$$\int_0^b \bar{N}_x dY + \sigma_x hb = 0 \quad (7b)$$

$Y=0, b$:

$$\bar{W} = \bar{\Psi}_x = 0, \bar{M}_y = \bar{P}_y = 0 \quad (7c)$$

$$\int_0^a \bar{N}_y dX = 0 \quad (7d)$$

where σ_x is the average axial compressive stress, \bar{M}_x the bending moment and \bar{P}_x the higher-order moment as defined in Reddy and Liu [9]. The in-plane boundary condition $\bar{V} = 0$ (on $X=0, a$) are fulfilled in an average sense as follows

$$\int_0^a \int_0^b \frac{\partial \bar{V}}{\partial Y} dY dX = 0 \quad (10a)$$

or

$$\int_0^a \int_0^b \left[\left(A_{22}^* \frac{\partial^2 \bar{F}}{\partial X^2} + A_{12}^* \frac{\partial^2 \bar{F}}{\partial Y^2} \right) + \left(B_{21}^* - \frac{4}{3h^2} E_{21}^* \right) \frac{\partial \bar{\Psi}_x}{\partial X} + \left(B_{22}^* - \frac{4}{3h^2} E_{22}^* \right) \frac{\partial \bar{\Psi}_y}{\partial Y} - \frac{4}{3h^2} \left(E_{21}^* \frac{\partial^2 \bar{W}}{\partial X^2} + E_{22}^* \frac{\partial^2 \bar{W}}{\partial Y^2} \right) + \frac{\bar{W}}{R} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \bar{W}}{\partial Y} \right)^2 - \frac{\partial \bar{W}}{\partial Y} \frac{\partial \bar{W}^*}{\partial Y} - (A_{12}^* \bar{N}_x^T + A_{22}^* \bar{N}_y^T) \right] dY dX = 0 \quad (10b)$$

For postbuckling analysis we need to establish postbuckling load-shortening relationships of the panel. The average end-shortening relationship is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Delta_x}{a} &= -\frac{1}{ab} \int_0^b \int_0^a \frac{\partial \bar{U}}{\partial X} dXdY \\ &= -\frac{1}{ab} \int_0^b \int_0^a \left[\left(A_{11}^* \frac{\partial^2 \bar{F}}{\partial Y^2} + A_{12}^* \frac{\partial^2 \bar{F}}{\partial X^2} \right) + \left(B_{11}^* - \frac{4}{3h^2} E_{11}^* \right) \frac{\partial \bar{\Psi}_x}{\partial X} + \left(B_{12}^* - \frac{4}{3h^2} E_{12}^* \right) \frac{\partial \bar{\Psi}_y}{\partial Y} - \frac{4}{3h^2} \left(E_{11}^* \frac{\partial^2 \bar{W}}{\partial X^2} + E_{12}^* \frac{\partial^2 \bar{W}}{\partial Y^2} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \bar{W}}{\partial X} \right)^2 - \frac{\partial \bar{W}}{\partial X} \frac{\partial \bar{W}^*}{\partial X} - (A_{11}^* \bar{N}_x^T + A_{12}^* \bar{N}_y^T) \right] dXdY \quad (11) \end{aligned}$$

In the above equations and in what follows, the reduced stiffness matrices $[A_{ij}^*]$, $[B_{ij}^*]$, $[D_{ij}^*]$, $[E_{ij}^*]$, $[F_{ij}^*]$ and $[H_{ij}^*]$ are reduced stiffness matrices which are functions of T , and determined through relationships [17]

$$\mathbf{A}^* = \mathbf{A}^{-1}, \mathbf{B}^* = -\mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{D}^* = \mathbf{D} - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{E}^* = -\mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{F}^* = \mathbf{F} - \mathbf{E}\mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{H}^* = \mathbf{H} - \mathbf{E}\mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{E} \quad (12)$$

where A_{ij} , B_{ij} , etc., are the shell panel stiffnesses, defined by

$$(A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij}, E_{ij}, F_{ij}, H_{ij}) = \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (1, Z, Z^2, Z^3, Z^4, Z^6) dZ \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \quad (13a)$$

$$(A_{ij}, D_{ij}, F_{ij}) = \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (1, Z^2, Z^4) dZ \quad (i, j = 4, 5) \quad (13b)$$

3 SOLUTION PROCEDURE

We assume that the solutions of Eqs. (1)-(4) can be expressed by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{W}(X, Y) &= \bar{W}^{**}(X, Y) + \dot{W}(X, Y), \\ \bar{\Psi}_x(X, Y) &= \bar{\Psi}_x^{**}(X, Y) + \dot{\Psi}_x(X, Y), \\ \bar{\Psi}_y(X, Y) &= \bar{\Psi}_y^{**}(X, Y) + \dot{\Psi}_y(X, Y), \\ \bar{F}(X, Y) &= \bar{F}^{**}(X, Y) + \dot{F}(X, Y), \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where $\bar{W}^{**} = \bar{W}_I^* + \bar{W}_{II}^*$, and \bar{W}_I^* is an initial deflection caused by lateral pressure that is lower than the buckling pressure, \bar{W}_{II}^* is an initial deflection due to initial thermal bending moment, and $\dot{W}(X, Y)$ is an additional deflection. $\bar{\Psi}_x^{**}$, $\bar{\Psi}_y^{**}$ and \bar{F}^{**} are, respectively, the mid-plane rotations and stress function corresponding to \bar{W}^{**} . $\dot{\Psi}_x(X, Y)$, $\dot{\Psi}_y(X, Y)$ and $\dot{F}(X, Y)$ are defined analogously to $\bar{\Psi}_x^{**}$, $\bar{\Psi}_y^{**}$ and \bar{F}^{**} , but is for $\dot{W}(X, Y)$. Note that $W_{II}^* = 0$ for cross-ply laminated cylindrical panels when the temperature field is assumed to be uniform distributed.

The prebuckling solutions \bar{W}^{**} , $\bar{\Psi}_x^{**}$, $\bar{\Psi}_y^{**}$ and \bar{F}^{**} are sought at the first step from the following nonlinear equations

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{L}_{11}(\bar{W}^{**}) - \tilde{L}_{12}(\bar{\Psi}_x^{**}) - \tilde{L}_{13}(\bar{\Psi}_y^{**}) + \tilde{L}_{14}(\bar{F}^{**}) - \tilde{L}_{15}(\bar{N}^T) - \tilde{L}_{16}(\bar{M}^T) - \frac{1}{R}\bar{F}^{**},_{xx} \\ + \bar{K}_1\bar{W}^{**} - \bar{K}_2\nabla^2\bar{W}^{**} = \tilde{L}(\bar{W}^{**}, \bar{F}^{**}) + q \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

$$\tilde{L}_{21}(\bar{F}^{**}) + \tilde{L}_{22}(\bar{\Psi}_x^{**}) + \tilde{L}_{23}(\bar{\Psi}_y^{**}) - \tilde{L}_{24}(\bar{W}^{**}) - \tilde{L}_{25}(\bar{N}^T) + \frac{1}{R}\bar{W}^{**},_{xx} = -\frac{1}{2}\tilde{L}(\bar{W}^{**}, \bar{W}^{**}) \quad (16)$$

$$\tilde{L}_{31}(\bar{W}^{**}) + \tilde{L}_{32}(\bar{\Psi}_x^{**}) - \tilde{L}_{33}(\bar{\Psi}_y^{**}) + \tilde{L}_{34}(\bar{F}^{**}) - \tilde{L}_{35}(\bar{N}^T) - \tilde{L}_{36}(\bar{S}^T) = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$\tilde{L}_{41}(\bar{W}^{**}) - \tilde{L}_{42}(\bar{\Psi}_x^{**}) + \tilde{L}_{43}(\bar{\Psi}_y^{**}) + \tilde{L}_{44}(\bar{F}^{**}) - \tilde{L}_{45}(\bar{N}^T) - \tilde{L}_{46}(\bar{S}^T) = 0 \quad (18)$$

To solve Eqs. (15)-(18) by means of a two-step perturbation approach [18], the solution \bar{W}^{**} may be determined in the same way as reported in [19].

Then an initially stressed laminated cylindrical panel is under consideration, and $\dot{W}(X, Y)$, $\dot{\Psi}_x(X, Y)$, $\dot{\Psi}_y(X, Y)$ and $\dot{F}(X, Y)$ satisfy the nonlinear equations

$$\tilde{L}_{11}(\dot{W}) - \tilde{L}_{12}(\dot{\Psi}_x) - \tilde{L}_{13}(\dot{\Psi}_y) + \tilde{L}_{14}(\dot{F}) - \frac{1}{R}\dot{F},_{xx} + \bar{K}_1\dot{W} - \bar{K}_2\nabla^2\dot{W} = \tilde{L}(\dot{W} + \bar{W}_T^*, \dot{F}) \quad (19)$$

$$\tilde{L}_{21}(\dot{F}) + \tilde{L}_{22}(\dot{\Psi}_x) + \tilde{L}_{23}(\dot{\Psi}_y) - \tilde{L}_{24}(\dot{W}) + \frac{1}{R}\dot{W},_{xx} = -\frac{1}{2}\tilde{L}(\dot{W} + 2\bar{W}_T^*, \dot{W}) \quad (20)$$

$$\tilde{L}_{31}(\dot{W}) + \tilde{L}_{32}(\dot{\Psi}_x) - \tilde{L}_{33}(\dot{\Psi}_y) + \tilde{L}_{34}(\dot{F}) = 0 \quad (21)$$

$$\tilde{L}_{41}(\dot{W}) - \tilde{L}_{42}(\dot{\Psi}_x) + \tilde{L}_{43}(\dot{\Psi}_y) + \tilde{L}_{44}(\dot{F}) = 0 \quad (22)$$

where $\bar{W}_T^* = \bar{W}^* + \bar{W}^{**}$. For convenience, we first introduce the following dimensionless quantities (with γ_{ijk} in Eqs. (30) and (31) below are defined as in Shen [10]).

$$\begin{aligned} x = \pi \frac{X}{a}, \quad y = \pi \frac{Y}{b}, \quad \beta = \frac{a}{b}, \quad \bar{Z} = \frac{a^2}{Rh}, \quad \varepsilon = \frac{\pi^2 R}{a^2} [D_{11}^* D_{22}^* A_{11}^* A_{22}^*]^{1/4} \\ (W, W^*) = \varepsilon \frac{(\dot{W}, \bar{W}^*)}{[D_{11}^* D_{22}^* A_{11}^* A_{22}^*]^{1/4}}, \quad F = \varepsilon^2 \frac{\dot{F}}{[D_{11}^* D_{22}^*]^{1/2}}, \quad (\Psi_x, \Psi_y) = \varepsilon^2 \frac{a}{\pi} \frac{(\dot{\Psi}_x, \dot{\Psi}_y)}{[D_{11}^* D_{22}^* A_{11}^* A_{22}^*]^{1/4}} \\ (M_x, P_x) = \varepsilon^2 \frac{a^2}{\pi^2} \frac{1}{D_{11}^* [D_{11}^* D_{22}^* A_{11}^* A_{22}^*]^{1/4}} \left(\bar{M}_x, \frac{4}{3h^2} \bar{P}_x \right), \quad \gamma_{14} = \left[\frac{D_{22}^*}{D_{11}^*} \right]^{1/2}, \quad \gamma_{24} = \left[\frac{A_{11}^*}{A_{22}^*} \right]^{1/2} \\ \gamma_5 = -\frac{A_{12}^*}{A_{22}^*}, \quad (\gamma_{T1}, \gamma_{T2}) = (A_x^T, A_y^T) R \left[\frac{A_{11}^* A_{22}^*}{D_{11}^* D_{22}^*} \right]^{1/4}, \\ (K_1, k_1) = \bar{K}_1 \left(\frac{a^4}{\pi^4 D_{11}^*}, \frac{b^4}{E_{22} h^3} \right), \quad (K_2, k_2) = \bar{K}_2 \left(\frac{a^2}{\pi^2 D_{11}^*}, \frac{b^2}{E_{22} h^3} \right), \\ \lambda_q = \frac{qa^4}{\pi^4 D_{11}^* [D_{11}^* D_{22}^* A_{11}^* A_{22}^*]^{1/4}}, \quad \lambda_p = \frac{\sigma_x Rh}{2} \left[\frac{A_{11}^* A_{22}^*}{D_{11}^* D_{22}^*} \right]^{1/4}, \quad \delta_x = \left(\frac{\Delta_x}{a} \right) \frac{R}{2[D_{11}^* D_{22}^* A_{11}^* A_{22}^*]^{1/4}}, \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

in which the alternative forms k_1 and k_2 are not needed until the numerical examples are considered, and A_x^T and A_y^T are defined by

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_x^T \\ A_y^T \end{bmatrix} \Delta T = - \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} \begin{bmatrix} A_x \\ A_y \end{bmatrix} (1, Z, Z^3) \Delta T dZ \quad (24)$$

where A_x and A_y are given in detail in Eq. (6).

The nonlinear Eqs. (19)-(22) may then be written in dimensionless form as

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon^2[L_{11}(W) + (K_1W - K_2\nabla^2W)] - \varepsilon L_{12}(\Psi_x) - \varepsilon L_{13}(\Psi_y) + \varepsilon\gamma_{14}L_{14}(F) - \gamma_{14}F_{,xx} \\ = \gamma_{14}\beta^2 L(W + W_T^*, F) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

$$L_{21}(F) + \gamma_{24}L_{22}(\Psi_x) + \gamma_{24}L_{23}(\Psi_y) - \varepsilon\gamma_{24}L_{24}(W) + \gamma_{24}W_{,xx} = -\frac{1}{2}\gamma_{24}\beta^2 L(W + 2W_T^*, W) \quad (26)$$

$$\varepsilon L_{31}(W) + L_{32}(\Psi_x) - L_{33}(\Psi_y) + \gamma_{14}L_{34}(F) = 0 \quad (27)$$

$$\varepsilon L_{41}(W) - L_{42}(\Psi_x) + L_{43}(\Psi_y) + \gamma_{14}L_{44}(F) = 0 \quad (28)$$

where $W_T^* = W^* + W_I^*$. It is worth noting that, for the case of $q=0$ then $W_I^* = 0$. In Eqs. (25)-(28), the non-dimensional linear operators $L_{ij}(\cdot)$ and the nonlinear operator $L(\cdot)$ are defined as in [10].

It is noted that we always have $\varepsilon < 1$ when $\bar{Z} = (a^2/Rh) > 2.96$, and in such a case, Eqs. (25)-(28) are of the boundary layer type. The governing equations (25)-(28) can then be applied to cases involving nonlinear prebuckling deformations, large deflections in the postbuckling range, and initial geometric imperfections of the panel simultaneously.

The boundary conditions expressed by Eq. (7) become

$x = 0, \pi :$

$$W = \Psi_y = 0, M_x = P_x = 0 \quad (29a)$$

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \beta^2 \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} dy + 2\lambda_p \varepsilon = 0 \quad (29b)$$

$y = 0, \pi :$

$$W = \Psi_x = 0, M_y = P_y = 0 \quad (29c)$$

$$\int_0^\pi \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} dx = 0 \quad (29d)$$

and the in-plane boundary condition expressed by Eq. (10b) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^\pi \int_0^\pi \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} - \gamma_5 \beta^2 \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} \right) + \gamma_{24} \left(\gamma_{220} \frac{\partial \Psi_x}{\partial x} + \gamma_{522} \beta \frac{\partial \Psi_y}{\partial y} \right) - \varepsilon \gamma_{24} \left(\gamma_{240} \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial x^2} + \gamma_{622} \beta^2 \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial y^2} \right) \right. \\ \left. + \gamma_{24} W - \frac{1}{2} \gamma_{24} \beta^2 \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial y} \right)^2 - \gamma_{24} \beta^2 \frac{\partial W}{\partial y} \frac{\partial W_T^*}{\partial y} + \varepsilon (\gamma_{T2} - \gamma_5 \gamma_{T1}) \Delta T_1 \right] dy dx = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

The unit end-shortening relationship can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_x = -\frac{1}{2\pi^2 \gamma_{24}} \varepsilon^{-1} \int_0^\pi \int_0^\pi \left[\left(\gamma_{24}^2 \beta^2 \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} - \gamma_5 \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} \right) + \gamma_{24} \left(\gamma_{511} \frac{\partial \Psi_x}{\partial x} + \gamma_{233} \beta \frac{\partial \Psi_y}{\partial y} \right) \right. \\ \left. - \varepsilon \gamma_{24} \left(\gamma_{611} \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial x^2} + \gamma_{244} \beta^2 \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial y^2} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \gamma_{24} \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial x} \right)^2 - \gamma_{24} \frac{\partial W}{\partial x} \frac{\partial W_T^*}{\partial x} \right. \\ \left. + \varepsilon (\gamma_{24}^2 \gamma_{T1} - \gamma_5 \gamma_{T2}) \Delta T_1 \right] dx dy \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Eqs. (25)-(31) may then be solved by means of a singular perturbation technique along with a two-step perturbation, and the postbuckling equilibrium paths may be determined to have the similar forms as

$$\lambda_p = \lambda_p^{(0)} - \lambda_p^{(2)} (A_{11}^{(2)} \varepsilon)^2 + \lambda_p^{(4)} (A_{11}^{(2)} \varepsilon)^4 + \Lambda \quad (32)$$

$$\delta_x = \delta_x^{(0)} - \delta_x^{(2)} + \delta_x^{(2)} (A_{11}^{(2)} \varepsilon)^2 + \delta_x^{(4)} (A_{11}^{(2)} \varepsilon)^4 + \Lambda \quad (33)$$

In Eqs. (32) and (33), $(A_{11}^{(2)} \varepsilon)$ is taken as the second perturbation parameter relating to the dimensionless maximum deflection, i.e.

$$A_{11}^{(1)} \varepsilon = W_m - \Theta_2 W_m^2 + \Lambda \quad (34)$$

where W_m is the dimensionless form of maximum deflection of the panel that can be written as

$$W_m = \frac{1}{C_{33}} \left[\frac{h}{[D_{11}^* D_{22}^* A_{11}^* A_{22}^*]^{1/4}} \frac{\bar{W}}{h} + \Theta_1 \right] \quad (35)$$

Although the solutions of Eqs. (32)-(35) have the similar forms as those in [10], but the symbols used in Eqs. (32)-(35) may have different expressions when initial pressure is under consideration. It is noted that $\lambda_p^{(i)}$ and $\delta_x^{(i)}$ ($i = 0, 2, 4, \dots$) are all functions of temperature.

Eqs. (32)-(35) can be employed to obtain the numerical results for full nonlinear postbuckling load-shortening and load-deflection curves of cross-ply laminated cylindrical panels subjected to axial compression combined with initial lateral pressure and resting on elastic foundations in thermal environments. If initial lateral pressure $q=0$, the buckling load of a perfect panel with movable straight edges can readily be obtained numerically, by setting $\bar{W}^*/h = 0$, while taking $\bar{W}/h = 0$ (note that $W_m \neq 0$). In this case, the minimum buckling load is determined by considering Eq. (32) for various values of the buckling mode (m, n) , which determines the number of half-waves in the X - and Y - directions.

4 NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numerical results are presented in this section for cross-ply laminated cylindrical panels resting on elastic foundations subjected to axial compression combined with initial lateral pressure. The material properties are assumed to be linear functions of temperature variation [20], i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} E_{11}(T) &= E_{110}(1 + E_{111}\Delta T), \quad E_{22}(T) = E_{220}(1 + E_{221}\Delta T), \\ G_{12}(T) &= G_{120}(1 + G_{121}\Delta T), \quad \alpha_{11}(T) = \alpha_{110}(1 + \alpha_{111}\Delta T), \quad \alpha_{22}(T) = \alpha_{220}(1 + \alpha_{221}\Delta T), \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

where E_{110} , E_{220} , G_{120} , α_{110} , α_{220} , E_{111} , E_{221} , G_{121} , α_{111} , and α_{221} are constants.

Typical results are shown in Figs. 2-4. For these examples, the panel has $a/b=1$, $a/R=1.5$, $R/h=30$ and $h=4$ mm. The material properties are assumed to be: $E_{110}=150$ GPa, $E_{220}=9.0$ GPa, $G_{120}=G_{130}=7.1$ GPa, $G_{230}=2.5$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=0.3$, $\alpha_{110}=1.1 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$, $\alpha_{220}=25.2 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$, and $E_{111} = -0.0005$, $E_{221} = G_{121} = G_{131} = G_{231} = -0.0002$, $\alpha_{111} = \alpha_{221} = 0.0005$. The postbuckling load-shortening and load-deflection curves for imperfect laminated cylindrical panels have been plotted, along with the perfect panel results, in Figs. 2-4. In these figures \bar{W}^*/h means the dimensionless forms of the maximum initial geometric imperfection of the panel. It is worth noting that there are two ways to plot the postbuckling load-deflection curves. One is using the dimensionless form of additional deflection \bar{W}/h , another one is using the dimensionless form

of total deflection \bar{W}_T/h . In the present study we use \bar{W}_T/h instead of \bar{W}/h , as reported in [10].

Figure 2 presents the postbuckling load-shortening and load-deflection curves of a $(0/90)_{2T}$ laminated cylindrical panel subjected to axial compression under different values of initial lateral pressure q ($= 0, 5$ and 10 MPa). Since $\Delta T = 0$, the postbuckling equilibrium path for a panel is still bifurcation type and is unstable when $q=0$. As can be seen in the case of initially pressurized panels, the deflections deviate greatly from those of a panel without any lateral pressure, and the net deflection for preloaded panels is smaller than that for a panel without any lateral pressure when the deflection is sufficiently large.

Figure 2: Effect of lateral pressure on the postbuckling behavior of a $(0/90)_{2T}$ laminated cylindrical panel subjected to axial compression: (a) load-shortening; (b) load-deflection.

Figure 3 presents the postbuckling load-shortening and load-deflection curves for a $(0/90)_{2T}$ laminated cylindrical panel subjected to axial compression combined with initial lateral pressure $q = 5$ MPa under different sets of environmental conditions $\Delta T = 0, 100$ and 200 °C. The results show that the postbuckling strength is decreased with increase in temperature. For all the cases of the panel in thermal environments, the postbuckling equilibrium path of pre-pressure-loaded laminated cylindrical panels under axial compression is unstable.

Figure 3: Effect of thermal environmental conditions on the postbuckling behavior of a pre-pressure-loaded $(0/90)_{2T}$ laminated cylindrical panel subjected to axial compression: (a) load-shortening; (b) load-deflection.

Figure 4 shows the effect of foundation stiffness on the postbuckling behavior of a $(0/90)_{2T}$

laminated cylindrical panel resting on elastic foundations subjected to axial compression combined with initial lateral pressure $q=5$ MPa. Three sets of foundation stiffness are considered. The stiffnesses are $(k_1, k_2)=(100, 10)$ for the Pasternak elastic foundation, $(k_1, k_2)=(100, 0)$ for the Winkler elastic foundation and $(k_1, k_2)=(0, 0)$ for the panel without an elastic foundation. As expected, the foundation stiffness increases the postbuckling strength but reduces the initial deflection of the $(0/90)_{2T}$ laminated cylindrical panel.

Figure 4: Effect of foundation stiffness on the postbuckling behavior of a pre-pressure-loaded $(0/90)_{2T}$ laminated cylindrical panel subjected to axial compression: (a) load-shortening; (b) load-deflection.

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Postbuckling behavior of shear-deformable laminated cylindrical panel subjected to axial compression combined with initial lateral pressure resting on elastic foundations in thermal environments has been presented based on a higher-order shear deformation theory. The material properties of laminates are assumed to be temperature-dependent. Numerical results demonstrate that the postbuckling strength of cross-ply laminated cylindrical panels is increased with increase in foundation stiffnesses, but decreased with increase in initial lateral pressure. The results show that the postbuckling strength is decreased, but the initial deflection is increased with increase in temperature. The results also confirm that the postbuckling equilibrium path is limit-point type for the cross-ply laminated cylindrical panel subjected to axial compression combined with initial lateral pressure.

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